

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SRIKRISHNA****FIRST NAME: BELLUR****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D QUIZ

1. What is a dissertation?

- A dissertation is a systematic investigation of a socially significant research question that contributes to the literature and demonstrates the skill of doctoral students to conduct original research.¹**
- A dissertation is a long essay describing any subject.
- A dissertation is an important literary composition.
- A dissertation is a technical document explaining how an experiment is conducted.

2. What is a dissertation prospectus?

¹ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Research* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 1.

A dissertation prospectus is a complete plan for executing the dissertation and is built upon the dissertation concept paper. The prospectus provides an opportunity for the supervisory committee to review the appropriateness of the research question based on the student's critical review of the literature.²

- It is a prospectus which offers different choices to the person reading it.
- It is a document giving details of the actual research conducted by a student.
- It is a document proposing what needs to be done at some future point in time.

3. What is Transparency in qualitative research?

Transparency is concerned with the evidence that a doctoral student is reasonably aware of and sensitive to potential positive and negative bias inappropriately influencing the findings. Personal insights gained from interactions with mentors, supervisors, counsellors, parents, and friends may enhance sensitivity to potential buyers when conducting dissertation research.³

- Transparency in qualitative research is the ability to easily read the dissertation.
- It is the possibility of guessing what the outcome of the research could be.
- It is the publication of evidence before the research concludes.

4. What is coherency in qualitative research?

² Sampson, 3.

³ Sampson, 41.

Coherency is concerned with accumulating evidence that multiple data sources and measures corroborate the dissertation research findings. This information helps the reader judge whether the findings are idiosyncratic to the perception or behaviour of a single research participant or idiosyncratic to the person of a single researcher as opposed to obtaining similar findings from multiple participants and researchers.⁴

It is the ability to construct sentences with correct grammar and syntax.

It is the quality of the dissertation in which each paragraph follows from the previous.

It is the quality of not making contradictory statements in the dissertation.

5. What is delimitation?

Delimitations are anticipated constraints in the interpretation of the findings of the dissertation research, whereas limitations are unanticipated constraints in data interpretation. Delimitation indicates the boundary with quasi-experimental research design regarding the lack of random assignment to groups that are known before the data are collected. While the research question indicates the scope of the dissertation, the delimitation will clarify what will not be examined.⁵

⁴ Sampson, 42.

⁵ Sampson, 49.

- Delimitation is the limitation imposed on the research due to the inability to find appropriate material.
- Delimitation is discontinuing the research project due to a lack of funds.
- Delimitation is the constraint upon the research conclusions due to direct or indirect inherent bias.

6. What is Potential for Researcher bias?

- Both quantitative and qualitative researchers need to acknowledge that the potential for bias exists in research. However, quantitative and qualitative researcher often take different positions on the likelihood of bias impacting their research. Quantitative researchers promote objectivity as a fundamental aspect of science and contend that it is possible to answer research questions without bias invalidating the result. Qualitative researchers contend that bias is inherent yet can be described clearly enough to allow the reader to judge if bias has inappropriately influenced the research.⁶**
- Researcher bias can arise because the researcher already has a fixed notion of the conclusion of the research.
- Researcher bias can arise by reading the wrong books or research papers contradicting the working hypothesis adopted by the researcher
- Researcher bias may arise when the researcher rejects the arguments in the research paper because of personal or national bias.

⁶ Sampson, 8.

7 What is academic research?

Academic research means a systematic inquiry process to answer a question the researcher and others want to solve. Research thus includes the steps involved in presenting and reporting it. To be a true researcher, one must share one's findings and conclusions with others.⁷

Academic research is discovering new ideas.

Academic research means searching again for what has already been discovered.

Academic research means reading new books to enlarge one's knowledge.

8) What are the reasons for citing resources?

There are at least four reasons to cite the resources: (i) To give credit whose idea and words have been taken; (ii) To reassure readers about the accuracy of the facts; (iii) To show readers the research tradition that informs the work of the researcher; and (iv) to help the reader follow or extend the research.⁸

To show that the proposition advanced in the research paper is supported by others.

To make the dissertation book scholarly and impressive.

To avoid allegations of plagiarism.

9) What are the two citation styles?

The two most common citation forms are Notes – bibliography style or Notes style, which is used widely in the humanities and in some social sciences. The

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth edition (Chicago: The University Press, 2018), 19.

⁸ Turabian, 139–40.

other style is the author-date style, used in most social sciences and in the natural and critical sciences. These two styles are often referred to as the Turabian or Chicago source citation system.⁹

- The two citation styles are direct citation and indirect citation.
- The two citation styles are giving the source's page number and not giving the source's page number.
- The two citation styles are citing in italics as against citing in bold letters.

10. What information is required in a citation?

- Even though citation style may differ in the element included and the format of the element, they must give the reader the information they need to identify and find the source. The information given must answer this question:**
- (i) Who wrote, edited or translated the text? In other words, who created it?**
- (ii) What data identify the text? This includes the title and sub-title of the work; volume number, edition number, or other identifying information; and page number or other locating information if the reference is to a specific part of a large text.**
- (iii) Who published the text, and in what context? This includes the name of the publisher, journal, or other entity responsible for making the text available and, in some cases, the title of any collection or series in which the work appeared.**

⁹ Turabian, 141.

- (iv) **When was the text published? This will consist of a year of publication and sometimes a season, month or specific day and sometimes time.**
- Just the name of the book or research journal.
- Only the name of the publisher and year of publication.
- Only the name of the author.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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